

Open APN Evolution of optical access node with all photonics – an operator's perspective

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Optical circuit switched time sensitive network architecture for high-speed passive optical networks and next generation ultra-dynamic and reconfigurable central office environments

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Central office's place in IOWN picture*

Current network configuration (typical)

IOWN configuration (example)

“new” or “renewal” Central Office

* Based on Jun-ichi Kani, « Update on the Innovative Optical and Wireless Network (IOWN) Initiative For Fixed Networks », workshop, ECOC2022

Central office's place in IOWN picture*

ROADM-based optical network

Open APN

1. Provision of control and management channels for TRx
2. Provision of turn-back connections between TRxs under the same Add/Drop
3. Support of typical access loss (e.g. 15 to 30 dB) and its variation

OLT role in existing Orange's Central office

FTTAntenna: The cell site gateway is connected by PtP to the OLT.

FTTEnterprise: the PtP connectivity is also privileged.

Synergy with FTTH:
A single OLT provides PON & PtP interfaces and a shared aggregation interface.

OLT : Existing functional blocks

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 1/6

Scenario 1 : APN interface of OLT's uplink ports

To be ready for 100Gbit/s or more line rate interface

APN-T : APN Transceiver

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 2/6

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 3/6

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 4/6

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 5/6

Possible Scenario: APN-G has a role at the optical front end of line card (PON and PtP)

OLT : Evolution of functional blocks 6/6

Scenario 6.: APN-G has a role at the optical front end of ONU (PON and PtP)

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OCTAPUS Goals (3 years – 2022/2025):

- Increase (switching) capacity at the Next Gen Central Office (NGCO)
- Efficiently support Disaggregated RAN (i.e. Fronthaul and TSN) and URLLC services.
- Consolidation of SDN with NGCO PHY layer
- Increase energy efficiency

Three Prototypes

- An SDN-/FPGA-controllable 16x16 Optical Circuit Switch-based photonic backplane
- A TSN-enabled Uplink Switch prototype with 800G (16x50Gb/s) TxRx intra-NGCO communication
- a TSN-enabled IF-card prototype interfaced intra-NGCO 800G TxRx & 800G PON TxRx

Key points for **All-Photonics** Central Office

1 OLT at Central Office has a key role for traffic aggregation and multiplexing. **Photonics** are the technologic companions for OLT functional blocks evolutions.

2 **Photonic backplane and new fiber** are important technologic steps for OLT with impact on power consumption, line rate, latency/jitter.

3 How **deep** will be the introduction of photonic function in optical access equipment? (here, 6 scenarios)

4 The mix of photonic routing (bypass) and electronic switching (Medium Access Control) require coordination with SDN **controller or orchestrator**.

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